

APPEARANCE OF ATOPIC DERMATITIS IN THE ORAL MUCOUS MEMBRANE AND LIPS IN PRE- SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Among allergic diseases in children, atopic dermatitis undoubtedly occupies one of the highest places. Atopic dermatitis is a disease that occurs equally in both sexes and in different age groups all over the world. According to various authors, the disease is widespread. [A. Baranov, 2011; Balabolkin, 2012; Lysikova, 1999]. Atopic dermatitis is often seen in the form of atopic cheilitis in dental practice. [Zykeeva, 2018] Currently, the etiopathogenesis and clinic of atopic dermatitis are well-studied, so it is possible to carry out diagnostic, etiotropic and pathogenetic treatment in children.

The purpose of the study. Appearance of atopic dermatitis in the oral mucous membrane and lips in pre-school children.

Material and methods. For the research, 20 patients under the age of 6 diagnosed with atopic dermatitis at the Republican Center for Allergology and Clinical Immunology were examined and anamnesis was collected. The examined patients were divided into 2 groups by gender: 9 girls (45%) and 11 boys (55%). Questionnaire and statistical processing methods were used in the study. Parents and caregivers of patients were informed about this study.

Results and discussion. 20 patients participating in the study were diagnosed with L20 atopic dermatitis according to MKB. The following symptoms of atopic dermatitis were observed on the face of the patients who applied: urticaria-15 (75%), nodule-3 (15%), erythematous-squamous rash-3 (15%), cracks in the corner of the mouth-2 (10%), tongue dryness-13(65%), tongue swelling-2(10%), lip skin transfer-1(5%), itching-4(20%), mucous membrane soreness-4(20%) hyperemia-5(25 %) papule around the lip-2(10%), itching-3(15%).

According to the results of the preliminary study, the frequency of occurrence of signs by gender was boys (55.5%) and girls (45.5%). It was found that these symptoms are 1.21 ± 0.2 times more common in boys than in girls.

Summary. Preschool children all have symptoms of atopic dermatitis on the face. The frequency of occurrence of symptoms took the lead in boys, and this indicator was 1.21 times more than in girls. According to the latest results of the study, it is necessary

for a dentist and an allergist to carry out the necessary therapeutic treatment to eliminate these symptoms.

Literature:

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